

Body awareness on postural sitting habits among college students in online classes

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Abstract

The risk of students being more exposed to poor posture and discomfort during school hours has become a problem when the threat of COVID-19 started. As the pandemic has made the government implement an online learning set-up as a new mode of learning, requiring the students to sit for a long period of time while the increasing rate of time consumed in technology usage, adds up to postural problems during online classes (Jolly, 2020). This was observed in a 2020 survey conducted by the American Chiropractic Association, with 92% of their patients were reported to experiencing muscle pain (such as back and neck pain) and as well as other musculoskeletal issues ever since the pandemic began, not exempting the children in these issues. With this, with the targeted United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals: good health and well-being and Ambisyon Natin 2040: Maginhawa, the research study discusses the difference in the college students' level of body awareness on postural sitting habits. The 5-point frequency Likert scale survey used in the study are adapted from the article entitled Back Health and Posture by Cleveland Clinic (2019) and other studies conducted by Daneshmandi et al. (2017), Schwertner et al. (2018), and Holland (2020). The survey questionnaires were divided into three sections: questionnaires about demographic profile, postural habits and sitting habits. The research findings say that the postural habits have high level of awareness with the frequency rate of 31.2% (125 respondents), on the other hand, medium level of awareness (59.9%) was shown to have highest frequency rate as seen in the data results of sitting habits. Therefore, after using Kruskal Wallis and Shapiro Wilk to know the significant difference between the respondents' demographic profile and their level of postural sitting habits, the results showed that there is a significant difference between postural habits and sex (p -value = 0.043) and as well as the level of eye gaze (p -value = 0.006) of college students. Thus, these results proves that the sex and level of eye gaze influence the level of awareness on postural habits of participants. With this, the researchers encourage the beneficiaries of the study to use the study's findings in analyzing the current situation faced by online students due to poor posture and sedentary lifestyle, and to recommend the future researchers to conduct further studies to explore the other contributing factors that could give the online learners and as well as the community, a view of self-awareness on their postural sitting habits while witnessing a comprehensive postural awareness widespread to lessen the prevalence of these in the society.

Keywords: Poor posture; Postural sitting habits; Online classes; Body awareness; Sedentary lifestyle.

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Introduction

In the Philippines, during a government-imposed lockdown, many people are forced to stay in their homes all the time, resulting in a sedentary lifestyle. A survey conducted in the third quarter of 2021 found that Filipinos' lifestyle has changed from being physically active to having sedentary behavior. Moreover, according to the respondents of the survey, they experienced headaches, back pain, muscle and joint pain, and felt more tired as their sedentary lifestyle continues. In line with this, the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Center for Disease Control concluded that these factors are some of the reasons why the pandemic significantly impacted people's lifestyles and ability to move. As a result, they encourage those who are confined to their homes to remain active cited in the article of Chua (2021). In addition, many businesses have moved to a work-from-home setup because of these sedentary lifestyle issues. This has led to health problems linked to improper posture and widespread ergonomic hazards for workers who are still adapting to the new set-up and still have problems with working equipment and furniture, as well as longer working hours than before (KMC Global Research, 2020).

According to a Facebook poll conducted earlier in year 2020 by the American Chiropractic Association (a leading association of chiropractors whose advocacy is primarily about chiropractic care), 92% of chiropractors reported an increase in neck, back, or other musculoskeletal problems among their patients since the pandemic started, including children (Jolly, 2020). With this, the demand for online classes in many schools requires children to sit for long periods of time, and the increasing use of technology only adds to the number of hours they are seated. Whereby, students are more compelled to sit in a fixed posture for the whole of their classes, daily, throughout their academic careers. Moreover, reduced physical activity and extended sedentary behavior are well-established to create more risk factors for both physical and mental health issues, including loss of muscular and cardiorespiratory fitness, weight gain, psychosocial difficulties, and even poor academic performance (Xiang et al., 2020). In relation to that, the article by the Remo (2020), entitled "*Preventing Online Learning Fatigue*," said that improper posture is contributing to muscle pains that Filipino students are experiencing during online classes. Thus, as reported, back pain is increasingly common in young people.

With that being said, the expert believed that students may be more vulnerable since they often do schoolwork from bed or the floor, hunched over computers for hours straight (Jolly, 2020). Accordingly, it is essential for students, teachers, and parents to have an understanding and to raise awareness of their postural habits and spinal health (Bettany-Saltikov et al., 2019). Thus, the researchers' goal will focus on physical activity promotion, and wellness to help solve postural problems (Salvo et al., 2021).

As the researchers have targeted to achieve one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) created by the United Nations, good health and well-being. These include encouraging people to live healthy, having an active lifestyle throughout their lives, and fostering partnerships between educational institutions and community-based sports organizations and clubs that are vital in achieving long-term educational outcomes that include health and well-being, according to the article written by Good Deeds Day in *Our Commitment to Sustainable Development Through Doing Good* (2021). Considering the aforementioned SDGs, which particularly good health and well-being, the researchers wanted to succeed and make a postural awareness widespread, as they will address those people suffering from improper posture by correcting them and by helping them achieve one of the United Nation's SDGs, the good health and well-being, one step at a time. Along with that, the Ambisyon Natin 2040: Maginhawa is also one of the goals the researchers want to achieve, which aimed to provide policies to promote work-life balance, hence, it is the best suitable way for promoting and living a healthy lifestyle among individuals and boosting safe physical activity during a pandemic (NEDA, 2016).

Finally, the outcomes of this study may aid in the possible development of appropriate interventions to assist in the correction of postural abnormalities among online class students, as citizens need to know about an illness and its symptoms for them to take preventive actions to avoid contracting it. Through this study, the researchers hope to educate other students about the critical nature of ergonomics when it comes to online classes. Hereby, the findings of the study will serve as a foundation for future health researchers to conduct precise assessments of the category of postural issues in students and those that require prompt medical attention. In addition, the researchers attempt to maximize advanced training and career opportunities in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) fields, expand its capabilities, workforce, and raise public scientific literacy.

Statement of the Problem

The primary purpose of this study is to know the difference in the level of the body awareness on postural sitting habits among college students in online classes based on their demographic profile. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents based on their:
 - a. Sex
 - b. Age
 - c. Body Mass Index
 - d. Student enrolled in Metro Manila City
 - e. Year Level
 - f. Courses
 - g. Numbers of subjects currently enrolled this semester
 - h. Time spent per day for online classes
 - i. Longest time spent in every subject during online class
 - j. Average time spent during online class
 - k. Gadgets used during online class
 - l. Level of eye gaze
2. What is the level of body awareness on postural sitting habits of college students during online classes?

3. What is the difference in the level of body awareness on postural sitting habits among students in online classes based on their demographic profile?

Scope and Delimitation

The researchers gathered data through an online survey form that consisted of different questions and was evaluated by two English instructors, Statistician, and five medical professionals. Additionally, the researchers started to distribute the online survey forms from mid-January until February 2022.

The study is intended to determine the level of body awareness on postural sitting habits among college students currently studying in any universities located in the National Capital Region. The survey will not be limited to certain ages as long as the participants are college students enrolled this S.Y. 2021-2022. Furthermore, the researcher chose college students as their respondents as they are the most exposed in online learning during pandemic and were predicted to have increased workloads compared to other grade levels.

Moreover, the researchers strictly did not include the other demographic such as the time spent in non-academic related activities and as well as time spent while standing. Additionally, participants must be using a chair and a table during online classes. Lastly, the researchers are not focused on health illnesses, so students who are clinically diagnosed with kyphosis, or lumbar lordosis, and other back and spinal injuries (that may contribute to improper posture) are also not acknowledged in the study.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a non-experimental descriptive research design in a comparative approach. This approach was used to determine the level of body awareness of participants on their postural sitting habits during online class sessions comparing it to their demographic profile. As defined by Siedlecki (2020), descriptive research design characterized persons, events, or circumstances by observing the natural state, furthermore, this also elaborated that descriptive study examined population's characteristics, uncovered issues within a unit, an organization, or a group of people, and investigated differences in features or practices across institutions or even nations.

Research Locale

This study takes place in different universities located at the National Capital Region (NCR) as this region is the home of well-known universities in the country specifically universities located in España, Recto or University Belt, Sta. Mesa, and Taft Avenue in Manila City. Furthermore, the respondents came from University of the Philippines – Manila, University of Santo Tomas, De Le Salle University and a few other well-known universities where there are many students that were utilized as the locale. These schools have large number of students who started engaging themselves in an online class platform, that made it easier for researchers to collect data. Since most of them met the standards to be one of the study's respondents, the variation of their responses was more manageable because the universities are clustered.

Sampling Design

The researchers come up with Simple Random Sampling as the method to be used in the study. According to Qualtrics (n.d.) and Thomas (2020), this method is the most often used type of probability sampling because it ensures that each participant has an equal chance, thus the final sample is unbiased and uncontrolled by the team and has great external authenticity when the sample size is substantial enough as it replicates the features of the broader population. With this, the researchers chose college students as their respondents studying within NCR. The National Capital Region is what the researchers chose since according to Fernandez and Federizo (2021), since the “new normal” started, it has increased the prevalence of a sedentary lifestyle among Filipinos in NCR. Thereupon, in the general population of college students at the universities, there must be a chance that someone may be chosen for inclusion in the sample by using simple random sampling (Laerd Dissertation, 2012). Using a statistical program called G-Power Software, the researchers arrived at a research sample size. Therefore, the researchers successfully gathered 401 respondents, excluding the 30 respondents used for pilot testing.

Instrumentation

The questionnaires were academically validated by statistician, two English teachers: Mary Ann Gole and Ericka Ilagan, and five medical doctors: Raymund Earnest Joseph Ona, Judea Tinsay-Paredes, Rabie Cinco, Ciara Lindt Oliva, and Rinalyn Feraren. The first part is questionnaires assessing the demographic profile of respondents based on the criteria of the study. Furthermore, this part asked the respondents to input their personal information needed for demographic profile. Moreover, the second part which is the questionnaires assessing the level of body awareness on habits were adapted from Daneshmandi et al. (2017), Schwertner et al. (2018), Cleveland Clinic (2019) and Holland (2020). These are divided into two sections, first is 11-item questionnaires assessing the postural habits. Secondly, is about sitting habits that consist of 12 questions about sitting habits. These questionnaires both have 5-point frequency Likert scale consisting of (1) Never, (2) Seldom, (3) Occasionally, (4) Often, and (5) Always.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before proceeding to the actual data gathering, the researchers made the survey validated by identified experts, following the survey validation is pilot testing. Afterwards, the researchers conducted a reliability test with their statistician after collecting the data gathered during pilot testing. During the month of January 2022 to February 2022, the researchers utilized their social media platforms to distribute the Microsoft Forms link of survey to their targeted participants who will meet the eligible requirements. The researchers have finally gathered 401 respondents in total. Following the data collection and cleaning of data, finally, the researchers will be conducting the data analysis.

Statistical Treatment

The data undergone Shapiro Wilk test, computed in IBM SPSS, failed to pass the normality test and therefore considered as non-parametric data. Therefore, the researchers used non-parametric statistical treatments, Kruskal-Wallis Test and Mann Whitney Test.

Kruskal-Wallis Test, according to Glen (n.d.), is a process to compare two or more groups to a distribution cut-off point. Hence, if the data in each type of demographic profile is consisting of more than 2 groups, to be compared to category of postural habits or sitting habits of respondents, the Kruskal-Wallis Test was used. Meanwhile, if the data is compared in only two groups, considering that the data is non-parametric, Mann-Whitney test is used. As defined, Mann-Whitney U test is an alternative to the independent sample t-test, therefore, it is a non-parametric test that compares two sample means from the same population and determines whether the data are equal or not (Mann-Whitney U Test, n.d.)

The study’s dependent variable is level of body awareness of college students on their habits, which is divided into two variables under, specifically, postural habits and sitting habits. The researchers, therefore, analyzed the data gathered to know if there is a significant difference in the level of body awareness on postural sitting habits based on their demographic profile. As demographic profile (consisting of sex, age, BMI, students enrolled in Manila, year level, courses, number of subjects currently enrolled this semester, time spent per day for online class, longest time spent in every subject during online class, average time spent during online class, gadgets during online class and level of eye gaze) have either two or more groups each category, the reason why there are two statistical treatments used for comparison.

There are three sections in the questionnaire: Section A: Demographic Profile, Section B: Questionnaires for Postural Habits, and Section C: Questionnaires for Sitting Habits.

In the questionnaires of Section B and C, used to determine the college students’ level of body awareness on postural sitting habits, 5-point Likert scale was used, with 5 (Always) being the highest score and interpreted as Complete Awareness, while 1 (Never) was considered as the lowest and was interpreted as Lack of Awareness. Furthermore, most of the statements in the questionnaire were stated in positively, however, the other statements which were observed as bad postural sitting habits undergone reversed scoring as it can alter the results needed if not. These negative statements helped the analysts to further analyze the respondents’ awareness on their habits. Instead of 5 (Always), 4 (Often), 3 (Occasionally), 2 (Seldom), 1 (Never), the least was interchanged to score the highest. This turned out to be 5 (Never), 4 (Seldom), 3 (Occasionally), 2 (Seldom), 1 (Always), due to the reason that the correct answer considered is when the respondent disagrees to the negative habits indicated in the question. Furthermore, in order for the researchers to know the statements with the highest and lowest score, they had computed the scores and discovered the results by checking the weighted mean of each statement.

Table 1 shows the interpretation of the level of body awareness on postural habits based on numerical rating and its verbal interpretation, as well as the interpretation of the level of body awareness on sitting habits with specific range and its verbal interpretation.

Table 1
Verbal interpretation based on their body awareness level on postural and sitting habits

Range	Verbal Interpretation
1-1.8	Lack of awareness
1.81-2.6	Low level of awareness
2.61-3.4	Medium level of awareness
3.41-4.2	High level of awareness
4.21-5	Complete awareness

Results and Analysis

Demographic Profile

The researchers gathered four hundred one (401) respondents for their survey in which 273 (68.1%) are female, and 127 (31.7%) are male. These respondents are college students aged 18 to 30 years old, with the majority aging from 18 to 25 as 399 (99.5%), followed by one (1) respondent (.2%) with ages ranging from 25 to 30. Two hundred thirty-five (235) of the respondents have normal Body Mass Index (BMI), while twenty-nine (29) were obese. Seventy-three (73) were underweight, while fifty-nine (59) were overweight. Three hundred twenty-nine (329) of the respondents who answered the survey were studying within Manila City, while seventy-two (72) were studying within NCR. The year level of one hundred ninety-nine (299) respondents are ranging from 1st to 2nd year college, on the other hand, one hundred ninety-eight (198) were 3rd to 4th year college students, while three (3) of the respondents were taking courses that takes five (5) to six (6) years in college. Eighty-nine respondents were taking Medical, Healthcare, and Life Sciences courses, which is the same as the number of respondents taking Social Science and Humanities courses. Eighty-four (84) were taking up Science and Engineering, while sixty-eight (68) were taking Business and Management. On the other hand, forty (40) respondents were taking Media and Communications, while thirty-one (31) were studying Computer Science and Information Technology.

The current number of subjects enrolled among the seventy-seven (77) respondents on the semester upon answering the survey ranged from 1 to 5, while 6 to 10 subjects were enrolled among two hundred eighty-four (4) respondents. Thirty (30) had 11 to 19 subjects enrolled while ten (10) were enrolled in 20 subjects and above. Hence, forty-eight (48) respondents spent less than 3 hours per day on online classes, while two hundred twelve (212) of the respondents spent three (3) to 6.99 hours per day. On the other hand, one hundred fourteen (114) respondents spent seven (7) to 10.99 hours per day on online classes, while twenty-seven (27) spent more than 10 hours. The longest time spent in every subject during the online class of the one hundred fifty-five (155) respondents was less than three (3) hours, while two hundred eighteen (218) spent 3 to 6.99 hours in every subject during an online class. Additionally, sixteen (16) respondents spent seven (7) to 10.99 hours, while twelve (12) spent more than 10 hours in every subject during an online class. The average time spent of one hundred forty (140) respondents during online class was less than 3 hours, while three (3) to 6.99 hours were spent by one hundred eighty-one (181).

Sixty-six (66) respondents spent 7 to 10.99 hours on average, while fourteen (14) spent more than 10 hours during online classes. The majority of the respondents (75.1%) used a laptop for the online class, while 14.7% use a mobile phone. Additionally, 7.7% used a computer during online class, while 2.5% of the respondents used a tablet or an iPad. This resulted in most of the respondents (56.9%) having a normal eye gaze, 36.7% had a lower eye gaze, and 6.5% had a higher eye gaze.

Level of Body Awareness on Postural Sitting Habits

Table 2
Level of body awareness on postural habits based on individual item

#	Postural Habits Statements	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	I sit upright with my back straight during online class.	3.14	0.91	Medium level of awareness
2	I sit with my upper body twisted sideways during online class.	3.86	1.11	High level of awareness
3	I sit with my body tilted forward during online class.	2.83	1.06	Medium level of awareness
4	I sit at the end of my chair and slouch completely during online class.	3.00	1.11	Medium level of awareness
5	I sit with my buttocks touching the back of my chair during online class.	3.10	1.17	Medium level of awareness
6	I sit with my buttocks well-supported without slipping forward during online class.	3.38	1.14	Medium level of awareness
7	During online classes, I sit with my feet flat on the floor.	3.01	1.19	Medium level of awareness
8	During online classes, I sit with my arms rested and at the same level as my elbows.	3.07	1.10	Medium level of awareness
9	I balance my body weight evenly on both hips while sitting during online class.	3.26	1.05	Medium level of awareness
10	When working at the computer, I hold my head up.	3.10	1.05	Medium level of awareness
11	To keep my wrists straight, I keep my elbows close to my body while sitting, at the same level as my computer desk.	3.16	1.01	Medium level of awareness

One hundred twenty-five (125) of the college students studying within NCR had a high level of awareness on postural habits. This was contradicted by Schwertner et al. (2018) in which they stated that an individual who remains seated for a long period of time, has a big probability of developing improper posture. This was opposite to this study's outcome wherein Filipino college students experiencing sedentary lifestyle showed high level of awareness in postural habits.

Table 3
 Level of body awareness on sitting habits based on individual item

#	Sitting Habits Statements	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	I sit in only one position throughout online class.	2.60	1.20	Low level of awareness
2	I sit with my back straight, supported by the backrest of my chair during online class.	3.10	1.04	Medium level of awareness
3	I sit with my back being supported by a pillow, or other back supports because my chair does not have backrest that can support my lower back's curve.	2.87	1.30	Medium level of awareness
4	I sit with my feet supported (e.g., Footstool).	2.31	1.36	Low level of awareness
5	I change my sitting positions throughout online class.	4.00	1.01	High level of awareness
6	I do some stretching exercises (at least every hour).	2.89	1.20	Medium level of awareness
7	I stand up for at least 30 seconds, after 20 to 30 minutes of sitting.	2.95	1.23	Medium level of awareness
8	I regularly change my leg position.	4.06	0.94	High level of awareness
9	I sit up straight and hold for a few seconds, improving the curve of my back as far as possible.	3.59	0.97	High level of awareness
10	I maintain a normal curve while sitting using a small, rolled-up towel or a lumbar roll in my back.	2.46	1.19	Low level of awareness
11	When sitting in a swivel, spinning, and revolving chair, I don't twist my waist while sitting. Instead, I turn my whole body.	2.73	1.23	Medium level of awareness
12	I sit with my hips supported on the chair and parallel to the floor.	3.13	1.03	Medium level of awareness

On the other hand, two hundred forty (240) of them had a medium level of awareness on sitting habits which was supported by various studies. Malanga (2019) stated that when an individual spends most of their time seated, the more probable it is for their posture to deteriorate. Schaefer (2017) backed this up by claiming that sitting can also have negative impacts on people's health and bodies in the short and long term, making an apparently innocent action potentially deadly.

Based on table 3, question number 8 under sitting habits got the overall highest weighted mean (4.06) corresponding to high level of awareness. On the other hand, the question that got the overall lowest weighted mean (2.31) is question number 4, also under sitting habits statements.

This proves that online students particularly college students studying within National Capital Region (NCR) has always change their leg position while sitting but has low score on how often they use a feet supporter while sitting.

Comparison between Body Awareness on Postural Sitting Habits and Demographic Profile

The p-value of .043 ($p > 0.05$) shows that there is a significant difference in the level of body awareness on postural habits among college students in online classes based on their sex. This, moreover, in relation to embodied cognition (how mind and body functions together) and how mood affects good postural habits (Giang, 2015), the study of Lewine (2011) discovered that mostly of the female participants who are academically strong students was discovered to have moderate to severe depressions scores associated to their poor academic. On the other hand, female operators who are computer users were reported to have a higher prevalence and incidence of musculoskeletal disorders than males (Toomingas et al., 2012). This contradicts to the p-value of .058 ($p > 0.05$) found in the body awareness level on sitting habits as compared to sex, which has no significant difference. As a result, there is a considerable difference in sex versus postural habits and sex versus sitting habits, it means that your habits in sitting is different and not influenced by the sex of individual, unlike in postural habits.

Both levels of body awareness on postural habits (p-value of .203) and sitting habits with a p-value of .272 ($p > 0.05$) of college students show no significant difference when both were compared to their age. This was the opposite of the results of the study conducted Kim & Lee (2019) demonstrating how oldness influences the ability of individuals to perform proper postural habits. Additionally, this also shows that the elderly have more risks of having difficulty doing certain tasks and cognitive deficits. Baudry et al. (2015), also stated there are progressive changes in postural susceptibility with age, which was explained in the article entitled Posture by Better Health Channel (n.d.) bad habits like slouching and inactivity cause muscle soreness which eventually leads to poor posture, as an individual progresses through life. This implies that elderly individuals spend more time sitting than younger people, as mentioned (Kim & Lee, 2019). As a result, there is a considerable difference in age versus postural habits and sitting habits, which contradicts the data. This is given, as seen that 99.5% of respondents are only from one age group (18 to 25), and the remaining .5% are from other different age ranges. It means that the demographic profile of respondents studying in NCR does not offer a variety of age groups.

The p-value of .329 ($p > 0.05$) shows that there is no significant difference between the level of body awareness on postural habits based on Body Mass Index (BMI), which is the same as the findings of level of body awareness on sitting habits when compared to BMI, showing no significant difference as well. Contradicting on the study by Pulsford et al. (2013) resulted on how obesity as participants' BMI is one of the factors affecting sitting habits and different postural deviations of respondents. Therefore, with the majority of college students having same BMI of normal (58.6%) in the sample population, the levels of their body awareness on both postural and sitting habits were not affected or influenced by BMI as there was no clear variety of BMI shown in the comparison process.

The p-value of .344 ($p > 0.05$) shows that there is no significant difference between the level of body awareness on postural habits based on whether there are enrolled in Manila City or any places in NCR region aside from Manila City, the same with the p-value of .573 ($p > 0.05$) or no significant difference on body awareness level on sitting habits basing it to the same demographic description mentioned. Which was according to De Baranda et al. (2020), assessing spinal alignment in sitting position among children found that demographic profile (age, height, sex, and weight) influenced the results but the places on where they are currently studying have no association. Banerjee & Chaudhury (2010) it was also mentioned in their study that respondents' location does not actually influence the variable of the study unless the research is population-based.

The p-value of .363 ($p > 0.05$), tackling on the difference of level of body awareness on postural habits based on year level of college students shows that there is no significant difference. It is the same with the findings gathered in level of body awareness in sitting habits of college students when compared to their year level, with p-value of .437 ($p > 0.05$) which means no significant difference as well. These findings were evident as seen in the related study of Ibrahim (2017) and article of Ross (n.d.). According to Ibrahim (2017) the study indicated that there is a correlation between college students' height, age, weight, self-image and other demographics and the prevalence of postural changes, but year level was not included as affecting factors. Moreover, Ross (n.d.) mentioned the reasons of having bad sitting habits does not also include the participants' year level as influencing factors.

When comparing the courses of respondents to the level of body awareness on their postural sitting habits, it shows that the p-value of .459 (postural habits) has no significant difference, the same with the p-value of .318 (sitting habits) showing no significant difference as well. Whereby, as per Alleyne (n.d.) and Kots (2021), the duration of the class may differ depending on the selected curriculum as certain courses demand a long time of studying, resulting in a prolonged period of sitting. Furthermore, even though time is consumed of by the students, on whether taking easier courses (shorter amount of time) or harder courses (longer amount of time), still serves as contributing factor to a sedentary lifestyle when a person usually sits while doing the tasks (Schwertner et al., 2018). The type of courses, moreover, does not affect the awareness on postural sitting habits of college students respondents during online classes.

The p-value of .173 ($p < 0.05$) shows that there is no significant difference in the level of body awareness on postural habits and the level of body awareness on sitting habits, with the p-value of .634 ($p < 0.05$), among college students in online classes based on the number of subjects currently enrolled this semester. Caromano et al. (2015), on the other hand, claim that most students spend a significant amount of time seated in front of their computers, both for studying and for leisure. As a result, it has been observed that such students had a high incidence of discomfort in the head, neck, shoulders, and trapezius muscle area. This discovery might be attributed to inadequate placement, inappropriate furniture, or even longer durations of sitting, all of which encourage incorrect postures, which promote improper postures and are related to how well they are aware of their postural sitting habits.

Hence, the observation made by Caromano et al. (2015) is contradicting the current study's results. Furthermore, sitting for a prolonged period of time increases pressure on the discs, thighs, and buttocks, along with poor posture, which greatly contributes to the formation of physical issues, weariness, and symptoms of discomfort, such as lumbar pain which is the most notable pain (Caromano et al., 2015).

The p-value of .745 ($p < 0.05$) shows that there is no significant difference in the level of body awareness on postural habits and in the level of body awareness on sitting habits, with the p-value of .8552 ($p < 0.05$), among college students in online classes based on the time spent per day for online class. However, in contrary to the current study's result, the human body structure does not adapt to sitting for long periods of time, being frequently mobilized, and/or being maintained in permanent static positions (Sampaio et al., 2016). Sitting for a long period of time can also affect standing and walking posture as it can lead to hamstrings, hip flexor, back, and core stiffness. Furthermore, according to the study conducted by Schwertner et al., (2018) when a person sits for an extended amount of time, they are more likely to acquire poor posture, which can lead to pain and health hazards. Regardless of how comfortable a person is at his or her work, prolonged and static posture is bad for the back (UCLA Health, n.d.) With this, with the given data which more than half of population of college students has time spent of 3 hours to 6.99 hours per day in online classes equates to prolonged sitting, is bad for the health but do not have such significant difference to habits relating to posture and sitting.

The p-value of .079 ($p < 0.05$) shows that there is no significant difference in the level of body awareness on postural habits and the level of body awareness on sitting habits, with the p-value of .149 ($p < 0.05$), among college students in online classes based on the longest time spent in every subject during online class which is contrary to the related literature showing that one key aspect affecting how a person carrying out their sitting posture is the time spent while sitting. Furthermore, according to Kots (2021), college course schedules provide further flexibility and self-rule, hence, rather of adhering to a predetermined quarter or semester plan, students may adjust their courses and class hours to fit their schedules. However, the duration of college courses varies per subject, although normally one credit equals one hour each week (Imm, 2020). Furthermore, some colleges let students enroll in three or more classes provided they maintain a minimum GPA as per (Cromwelle, 2022). With this, the results in the current study show no significant difference, as mentioned by other supporting studies, college students have flexible schedules on every subject they take.

The p-value of .711 ($p < 0.05$) shows that there is no significant difference in the level of body awareness on postural habits and the level of body awareness on sitting habits, with the p-value of .727 ($p < 0.05$), among college students in online classes based on the average time spent during online class. In contrast to Casas et al. (2016), online students study coursework for many hours each day in front of a desktop computer or laptop, which numerous students have adopted to. Eventually complain of significant discomfort in their backs, shoulders, and neck muscles as a result of looking down or straining for extended periods of time. This is because excessive time spent in front of these gadgets leads to poor posture and may result in physical ailments.

Furthermore, it is found that time spent in academic activities, including inside and outside the classroom (21 8.5 hours/week) and computer screen time (17.9 12 hours/week), is linked with acute and long-term back and neck pain the day of the evaluation (Online Schools Center, n.d.). Predominantly, two (2) hours or more of average time spent working can already cause back and neck pain and is intimately associated with a decreased risk of abdominal overweight/obesity. Furthermore, with the sample college students in NCR who answered the survey indicated that they are spending an average time of three (3) to 6.99 hours, they are most likely to be experiencing back and neck pain which greatly affects the process of them carrying out their postural sitting habits, but still not the level of their awareness in doing it.

The p-value of .666 ($p < 0.05$) shows that there is no significant difference in the level of body awareness on postural habits and sitting habits, with the p-value of .258 ($p < 0.05$), of college students in online classes based on the gadgets used during online class. Contradicting in what Patterson et al. (2021) stated that the user's posture may be slouched when reading on a laptop or computer and when the gadgets' screen is probably too low. Hence, since most of the college students indicated that they have normal level of eye gaze (56.9%) while using their laptops (75.1% users), therefore, the gadgets that they are using during online class do not have significant difference when compared to their awareness on postural sitting habits.

The p-value of .006 ($p > 0.05$) shows that there is a significant difference in the level of body awareness on postural habits among college students in online classes based on the level of eye gaze. As one's postural habits change as a result of the frequently uneven level of gaze that one needs to adjust to in order to accommodate the locations of the object being targeted (Bédard et al., 2008; Shieh & Lee, 2007). Furthermore, a person's postural motion can be affected by the height at which their eyes are focused (Ustinova & Perkins, 2011). On the other hand, the p-value of 0.996 ($p < 0.05$) shows that there is no significant difference in the level of body awareness on sitting habits among college students in online classes based on the level of eye gaze. It was applied by Princeton University (n.d.) that it is possible that users spend the majority of their waking hours at their desks and that they should consider making their workspace a more comfortable environment for both short and long-term health reasons. In order to avoid poor sitting habits, it is recommended that individuals arrange their most frequently used things at eye level, such as their laptop computer (Princeton University, n.d.).

Conclusion

College students are prone to having improper posture as they are most likely to lead sedentary lifestyle this pandemic due to online class. Their body awareness on postural sitting habits affects their posture, health, and lifestyle. This study concludes that:

1. The fact that most of the college students studying within NCR showed high level of awareness regarding their postural habits, does not automatically mean they have proper posture.
2. College students who use ordinary chairs during online class are more prone to developing improper posture, when compared to those who utilize ergonomic chairs during online class.

3. College students studying within NCR have low level awareness of the importance and benefits of using a rolled-up towel or lumbar roll in their back while seated.
4. College students studying within NCR have a low level of awareness on the importance of foot support while sitting. Sitting with their back straight is the only habit they're aware of to maintain proper posture.
5. The appropriate height of the chair and table depends on each user, as this is also a factor that may contribute to their posture while sitting during online class.
6. The mood affects how the body moves and as well as their habits, in which was observed to most female having the tendency to suffer in mental disorders which results to having consistent prevalence of musculoskeletal disorder due to poor sitting habits.
7. Prolonged sitting can affect not only the sitting posture but also the posture of people while in a standing position. Furthermore, regardless of their comfort, it is still considered harmful when they engage in prolonged sitting.
8. Despite college students having flexible subject schedules, prolonged sitting is not avoided. This might not be identified at the beginning, however, eventually, discomfort complaints will arise due to down or straining positions for extended periods of time. This results in poor posture which can affect students' school performance negatively.
9. With the college students studying in NCR who answered the survey indicated that they are spending an average time of three (3) to 6.99 hours, they are most likely to be experiencing back and neck pain which greatly affects the process of them carrying out their postural sitting habits, but still not the level of their awareness in doing it.
10. The height where the eyes focus has a significant effect on the posture of an individual. This is because the angle of where the eyes gazes can impact a person's posture and motor performance.

Recommendations

As the researchers did not put much focus on the level of eye gaze that was included in the study's demographics. Thus, it can be recommended for future researchers to further expand the data by assessing muscle pain on the relationship of eye gaze in maintaining a proper posture. In addition, as gadgets have been a necessity in today's modern world, hence, it is recommended to future researchers that they can use the study's data regarding the type of gadgets used by students in relation to level of eye gaze and muscle pain.

Considering that the majority of survey questions and components of studies and assessments involve sitting, future researchers must consider and incorporate the type of chairs and tables or amenities in general as part of the assessment. In addition, college students' time while seated are not only spent in academic related activities but also in extracurricular activities in their organizations, thus, the time spent on non-academic related activities must be included in the study as well.

Since the pandemic started, online learning was implemented requiring people especially students to engage in sedentary lifestyle. Therefore, it is recommended that students should be taught in school and at home to stand for at least one minute to stretch their muscle every 20-30 minutes of sitting, on whether during online class discussion or doing leisure activities at home while seated.

The researchers recommend future studies to look into other various factors that may contribute as to why despite an individual's basic awareness of their postural and sitting habits, continue to engage in bad habits that result in having a poor posture. Thus, the following factors are possible causes of students' poor postural sitting habits that needs further research:

- a. The difference on the level of comfort among individuals who uses ergonomically designed chairs, foot support, and back support versus those who uses only ordinary chairs.
- b. The possible more risks, short and long-term effects that are evident among online students in the next few years while seating in the same position for a long period of time.

According to several studies, the female population is more prone to improper posture due to the sex and awareness level of postural patterns. Furthermore, the researchers are encouraging the future researchers to further study into how different sitting position or sitting postures might be used as an indicator of numerous mental problems experienced by female, while making this research study as one of their main bases and by analyzing the current situation of Filipino female students, relating it to the prevalence of mental conditions presented in other studies. This will help future researchers understand why and how the frequency of musculoskeletal problems and bad posture is rising among females.

The University Management Department/Student Body must develop educational courses to increase student understanding to the benefits, hazards, and concerns associated with improper posture and sitting habits. By implementing educational courses in schools and universities (private or public), every Filipino community will be more aware and concerned about the rising rate of musculoskeletal disorders and their effects, and everyone will no longer consider poor posture and sedentary lifestyle as ordinary topics, but rather a serious issue.

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